

Yashil

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, siyosiy, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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FOOD SECURITY PROBLEMS

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Abstract: This is it in the article our country population good quality food products with provide and food safety problems, main directions explained.

Key words: Food security, village economy product, ecological clean products, stability, world, population, hunger, production release.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada mamlakatimiz aholisini sifatli oziq-ovqat mahsulotlari bilan ta'minlash va oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlash muammolari, asosiy yo'nalishlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, qishloq iqtisodiyoti mahsuloti, ekologik toza mahsulotlar, barqarorlik, dunyo, aholi, ochlik, ishlab chiqarish hajmi.

Аннотация: В статье описаны основные направления и проблемы обеспечения населения нашей страны качественными продуктами питания и обеспечения пищевой безопасности.

Ключевые слова: Продовольственная безопасность, сельскохозяйственная продукция, экологически чистая продукция, устойчивость, мир, население, голод, объем производства.

INTRODUCTION

It is known that a person organism for to live and development for food of products place it is very necessary . Next in years the world scale of the climate sharp level change , ecological situation deterioration , the world scale demographic indicators orb to go as a result food products and his safety has been requirements more and more to increase reason is happening

The world scale of the population increased to go not only food products , socio-economic cases too serious effect shows. Food safety very wide meaning concept being the first in line independent of the state another to the states exactly food products relatively depends, that is subordinate that it is not means Also, the population the need physiological standards suitable respectively consumption goods with enough level to provide mean holds

Last in years of the climate more and more change due to lands salinity increased is going on. Of the soils of the structure to change reason is happening Developed and developing countries food products cultivation regarding take going efficient to the activity despite , food products work release of size growth population the number from growth behind It remains while village farm development for enough conditions there is didn't happen countries problem more and more deepening that he is going is showing .

UN of Food and village economy organization and The whole world Health Save organization information according to the present at the time out of 840 million in the world more than person, that is almost each 8 of a person one fed up not eating Most last studies while planet of the population 30% from increases fed up not eating due to the most main trace element and vitamins lack of from the problem suffering smoking 52 in the country of hunger "serious", "exciting" degrees note done is showing . From hunger suffering smoking of the population most, that is , 520 million excess Asians that to emphasize it is permissible .

Population the number fast increased going food products work release possibilities being limited because of many countries population good quality food with provide issue main to the problem is spinning .

Uzbekistan Republic of in the years of independence Village economy in the field very big achievements to hand entered , including village economy products work release size 2 equal to increased .

In our country food safety provision of citizens health and his life improvement of society socio-economic situation stable development , national safety and country independence stable save main directions to one became In this regard In the Republic population good quality food products with stable provision, village economy products growers support – support according to strategic in terms of purposeful and consistent measures done is increasing .

Uzbekistan Republic of President Shaukat Miromonovich Mirziyoyev by 2017 year on February 7 signed "2017-2021 in years Uzbekistan Republic development 5 ta priority directions according to Actions strategy"

about Decree the economy development and of liberalization priority directions too food safety separately attention oriented , structural changes deepening and village economy work release consistent develop , country food safety more strengthening , ecological clean products work release expand , of the agricultural sector export potential significant level increase priority task as marked .

President for 2019 intended the most important priority tasks about In the Address of the Oliy Majlis "Village". in the farm from reforms the goal is economic benefit to see with together with food safety provide and people well-being from raising consists of the fact that note done according to Ministers Court "2019 – 2024 in years in our country food – food safety provide national program confirmation about" gi decision project work released. This of the decision performance today's in the day in our country food safety in providing program action being service does

this regard the following food safety of provision main directions reached is defined as :

food safety in the field architectural and legal base improvement ;

village to the farm intended lands and water resources reasonable use

main kind of village economy and food products, raw materials internalwork release stable development ;

livestock, poultry, fishing field stable development, product work release volumes increase , food base strengthening ;

village economy and food products work release infra structure improve

food products safety provide ;

population all layers food products with to be provided foreconomic opportunities increase

food safety to provide state by in order put and control to do

Specialists to emphasize according to 2022 year January-September months village, forest and fishing economy products (services) . common volume is 248.6 trillion soum or 2021 suitable to the period compared to 3.6 % to increased

State statistics committee information according to 2022 year 9 in the month cultivated farming products in size vegetables leadership is doing – 8 million tons This indicator the rest products in the section as follows :

grain products – 6.7 mln tons ; potatoes – 2.6 mln tons ;

policy crops – 1.6 million tons ;

fruit and berries – 2.2 mln tons

grapes – 1.4 mln tons

In our country done being increased of reforms present stage fruit - vegetable farming long for a period of time stable development providing network efficiency increase through food products has been demand satisfy, his safety supply, export expand and of our people marriage conditions enable gives

The population good quality food products with enough level provide country food food of safety one part is considered The population main food types has been needs to satisfy food price and quality harmony provide and food safety state by guaranteed socio-economic development main from the conditions is one

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